

LINGUOCULTURAL UNIQUENESS: THE TRANSLATION OF I.YUSUPOV'S POETRY

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Annotation: The article focuses on the linguocultural aspects of translating the poetry of the prominent Karakalpak poet Ibrayim Yusupov. It discusses the challenges of translation, such as conveying national imagery, metaphors, rhythm, and cultural codes. Strategies are highlighted that help preserve the aesthetic and cultural value of the original text.

Key words: Ibrayim Yusupov, Karakalpak poetry, linguocultural features, folklore elements, metaphors, national identity, translation, cultural context, traditions, symbolism.

The poetry of Ibrayim Yusupov, an outstanding Karakalpak poet, is a unique combination of deep national identity and universal human themes. His works are filled with the richness of the Karakalpak language, subtle metaphors and images that reflect the traditions, customs and worldview of Karakalpak people. Translating such poetry requires not only a deep knowledge of the language, but also immersion in the cultural context. The "People's poet of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan" (This title is an honorary designation awarded to distinguished poets for their significant contributions to Uzbek literature and culture) I. Yusupov expresses his love for his homeland in the poem "Bu yerlar hali zo'r bo'ladi". The value of the country where a person was born and raised, and his attitude towards it begin with a clash of feelings of disbelief in rumors and hope for the future:

*Mishmish bor: qoraqalpoqlar
Ko'p vaqt o'tmay ko'char emish,
Yaxshi yerga qo'nmoq uchun
Qushlar kabi uchar emish.*

In ancient times, the Karakalpaks were a nomadic people, primarily engaged in livestock breeding. At the same time, he explained that the Karakalpaks enriched their culture, developed art, literature and folklore. Ibrayim Yusupov's poems harmoniously intertwine national motifs and philosophical depth. The main features of his poetry include:

Use of folklore elements. Yusupov's poems often contain images taken from Karakalpak fairy tales, epics and traditional songs.

Metaphoricity. His poetic language is saturated with metaphors, allegories and symbols, which often have a cultural connotation.

National identity. The poet subtly conveys the features of the Karakalpak worldview through images of nature, native land and people.

Translating I. Yusupov's poetry into another language, especially into English, faces a number of challenges. Metaphors and allegories, characteristic of I. Yusupov's poetry, are deeply rooted in Karakalpak culture. The translator faces the challenge of conveying their meaning without losing the artistic perception. Sometimes it is necessary to adapt or create new images that retain the original impact. Unique elements of Karakalpak culture, such as references to specific traditions, folk festivals or local realities, may be unfamiliar to the reader of another language. Here the translator must find a balance between explaining the context and preserving the poetic form.

Each of the I. Yusupov's works is characterized by its own artistic and linguistic qualities. A talented written work has a special secret in itself. Thus, a writer's style is built from the many "secrets" in his works.

That is why it is called a system of systems. At the same time, the writer's style serves as a basis for defining it and correcting the system of systems. When studying a writer's language and style, that foundation must be the focus of attention.

The style and language of I. Yusupov's prose are characterized by the following features:

- it is clear and concise, expressing deep thoughts and ideas in a few words;
- its lexical basis is the skillful use of words from the vernacular, raising it to a level of remarkable artistic excellence;
- the poet is not limited to any one lexical layer, his linguistic range is wide and rich (*"I. Yusupov is a unique poet with a rich language and fiery emotions," says Zulfiya.*);
- there is no artificial artifice in the writer's style;
- in every prose work, sentences are only minimally proportional;
- the sentence structure is quite simple, mostly simple sentences;
- the connecting role is played by noun and verb phrases.

In order to analyze the translation of the poet's prose, we studied the versions translated by R. Rzaeva (the poet's daughter-in-law).

"Tomaris" is considered to be "Jeanne Dark" in I. Yusupov's prose []. It shows the period when the Karakalpak people were ruled by Tomaris – the Sun's daughter. In terms of the truth of the content and the skill of storytelling, this work is an example of artistry.

The play begins with Tomaris's grief of the mother as a result of the loss when her child becomes a prisoner in the hands of her enemy Kaygisrav, where her child's disobedience to the enemy is described by one of the soldiers. The translation opens with this very narrative tone. There are many things in the first section that require careful consideration.

The translator measures each of these, taking some without any changes depending on the content and language of the work, others he takes exactly from the spoken language of the foreign language, and the third directly from the literary language.

*Tumarisa, wa anajan,
Sarsilasan basm iyip.
Perzentiniñ azasman,
Júrek-bawırnı tur góy kúyip.
Enkeytpe tilla jađmıdı,
Sır berip nasharlıq etpe [].*

Rzaeva's translation:

*Tomiris! Mother's grief
Bows a proud head down,
Strong pain in the heart,
And emptiness in the look around,
Tomiris! Your grief is heavy
But remember about the queen's crown
Don't show a woman's weakness and groan.[]*

The translator's skill is evident in the fact that she fully revealed the author's thoughts and tried to preserve Yusupov's style. In addition, several examples of the translation of the poet's works can be given.

In conclusion, Ibrayim Yusupov's poetry is a unique bridge between cultural identity and universal themes. Translating his poems requires a deep understanding of the language, culture and philosophy in order to preserve the emotional power and national flavor of the original. In translation, the translator's opinion, knowledge, and level of language proficiency are very important. For this reason, the study of such scientific works should be continuous.

References:

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